

AWARENESS OF THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA AMONG STUDENTS: MALAYSIA AND INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

The development of social media applications such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and soon have been adapted in various fields such as education, politics and business. This study aims to identify the level of awareness of the use of social media on security issues among Malaysian and Indonesian students. This study is in the form of a survey using questionnaires and the sample involved is a total of 414 people randomly selected from among students in Malaysia and Indonesia. Data analysis for this study is using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. The study found that the majority of users have awareness and know about privacy and information security issues when dealing online, especially through social media. Therefore, this study suggests that consumers should be more careful about security and privacy issues when sharing personal information, especially information related to online business.

Keywords: media social, awareness, security issue

Introduction

The development of the Internet, Web 2.0 and communication technology provides users with the opportunity to actively interact through various applications connected to the Internet wirelessly and wirelessly. Today, various applications are developed to provide users with the opportunity to communicate, access, share, and disseminate information to other users around the world. The advancement of the Internet and communication technology in Malaysia has had such a huge impact on the lives of people today. For example, communication technology provides opportunities for individuals and organizations to increase efficiency in day-to-day operations, improve productivity and competitiveness in various fields such as politics and economics (Yusuf, Ashari, & Razalli, 2018).

In addition, the development of online systems or applications also brings changes to the daily life of the community in the processing, sharing and dissemination of information (Salleh, Salman, Ali, & Hashim, 2016). In addition, the development of such technology also accelerates the formation of a new 21st century society, namely digital society or network society. According to Castells (2011), the network community refers to the basic structure of a society that is closely related to the information society that uses the infrastructure and application of communication technology to perform their daily work.

M.Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) described social media applications as a media formed based on social interaction and built to facilitate the process of access and access to shared information. Social media based on the use of the Internet and Web technology allows one-way media broadcasting systems to be transformed into more active and interactive dialogue systems. The more interactive nature of social media with the presence of interactivity features can increase the satisfaction of online communication (Salleh, 2012) and cause it to be unique and more dynamic content compared to other media. Social media also gives users the space and power to express themselves and connect with other individuals easily (Gerbaudo, 2018).

Surveillance on social media can be done by friends of social media users themselves or third parties such as spammers (Ali et al., 2018). Typically, other users on social media have the opportunity to send spam or impersonate one of their friends to monitor or obtain a user's personal information on social media. Today, social media users are eager to share content but are unaware of the implications or risks when publicly displaying personal information. Personal information on social media is open to the risk of misuse of information by cybercriminals to disguise using real user identities for fraudulent activities. In fact, cybercrime victims are unaware of their identity and personal information being monitored, used or stolen until they become victims (Baccarella, Wagner, Kietzmann, & McCarthy, 2018).

The issue here is, the extent to which users, especially students in the use of social media applications in Malaysia and Indonesia have the experience, awareness, understanding and knowledge that there is a concept of surveillance that can interfere with privacy when using it. Do users know of other users who are watching what is being shared? To what extent do users accept and understand surveillance issues through these social media applications bring positive and negative effects in daily life? Therefore, the purpose of this article is to discuss the user experience of social media applications among University students on the issue of supervision.

Phenomenon of Social Media Use

Information from Go-Gulf.com shows that the global online population is close to 30% of the world's population with almost two billion users and they spend 32 hours every month with the Internet (GO-Gulf, 2012). The largest online population is in Asia with 922 million users

while North America recorded the highest online penetration rate of almost 79%. With the presence of social networking sites such as Myspace and Facebook, social media has become one of the most popular Internet services as it allows the development, creation, dissemination, and use of information and entertainment quickly and easily by both organizations and individuals (Wollan, Smith, & Zhou, 2011). The use of social media has become a global phenomenon nowadays and Asia is the largest market in terms of consumer participation. In fact, according to the Nielsen report, the growth in the use of social media in Asia Pacific is very encouraging and is now the most critical trend in the online sector. This is because this media is used for a variety of reasons. Among them are information and feedback channels, product innovation, promotion and advertising, as well as training and education. Its use varies from place to place and is based on demographics (Arno, 2012).

In Asia Pacific with 456 million users, one-third of the world's online population is engaged in social media activities. In fact, the penetration rate of social networks in Brunei, Hong Kong, South Korea, and Singapore exceeds 50%, which exceeds the regional average rate of 20%, while India has a consumer market of 82 million people. Social media such as microblogging, social networking, corporate blogs, and video sharing are important channels for corporate marketing and communication in Asia. In China, for example, 80% of companies actively use microblogging and show a 10% increase between 2010 and 2011 (Barkhuus & Tashiro, 2010).

Social Media in Malaysia and Indonesia

With over 17 million Internet users in Malaysia and 40 million in Indonesia, social media in these two allied countries is also growing rapidly, especially among "netizens". This new media technology is seeing more and more people getting involved in the cyber world in various ways in various roles and responsibilities (Chan, 2012). People are no longer limited to blogs alone; even among the early recipients of social media have various accounts covering blogs, Twitter, and video sharing platforms.

The use of social media shows an increase in both consumers and businesses. With the advancement of technology, mobile devices, especially mobile phones, are becoming one of the main mediums for accessing this new media. A study by M.Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) found that on average Malaysians spend up to 103 minutes per day through mobile devices and access to social media ranks third (16%) apart for entertainment and games (Digitalinfluencelab, 2021). A report released by Nielsen (2019) shows that access to mobile phones and desktops by Malaysian households is the same, at 77%, less than 2% compared to laptops while tablet use involves 18%. This is quite different from Indonesia which recorded the highest percentage in mobile phone usage, which is 78% compared to desktop computers (31%) and laptops (29%). This is because Indonesia is the third largest mobile market in Asia Pacific after China and India, with 235.8 million customers as of the end of 2010 with 30 million mobile Internet users (Nurhayati-Wolff, 2021).

Therefore, social networking has become a popular activity in the life of the community not only in Indonesia, but also in Malaysia with a usage rate of 87% respectively (Malaysian

Communications And Multimedia Commission, 2020). This is followed by watching videos, sharing photos, and blogs. Twitter users in Indonesia make up about 15% of the world's total tweets and this makes it the third largest country of Twitter. In addition, Indonesia is also the second largest Facebook user in the world after the United States in fact, two-thirds or 70% of Facebook users access the site via mobile phone. The Indonesian community is also very fond of blogs with more than five million blogs as of May 2011 in addition to more than 20 blogger communities throughout Indonesia (Nurhayati-Wolff, 2021).

Purpose of the Study

In today's world, social media is becoming increasingly important. Users can utilise social media platforms to explore, produce, share, and discuss, and are able to condense among themselves while also allowing for virtual self-presentation and self-disclosure. In fact, while many researches on awareness of the students toward social media have been undertaken, it is important to review this matter over time. The aim of this study was to explore the awareness of the use of social media among Malaysian and Indonesian higher education institution students based on their personal data-sharing and attitude while browsing the social media and their trust towards online information. A comparison between the two countries' result was conducted based on the online learning sessions in 2021 and to prepare an instrument that could be used by researchers and universities. Furthermore, by understanding the level of awareness of the students toward social media can serves the positive results toward education and social interaction among them. The research questions were:

What were the demographic considerations related to Malaysian and Indonesian students' views towards the awareness of the use of social media?

What were the main reason for Malaysian and Indonesian students to surf the internet and social media?

1. What were the differences that existed between Malaysian and Indonesian students on the level of awareness towards social media usage?

Research Design

This study quantitative research was conducted using a survey design to assess the extent of selection of social media types as well as the level of awareness towards the use of social media among Malaysian and Indonesian students. The four sub-sections included instrument, data collection, participation, and data analysis.

Instruments

This survey consisted of five (5) parts: Part A contained the demographic profile of the respondents; Part B referred to the analysis of social media usage; Part C was pertaining to personal data sharing; Part D concerned the student attitude on social media; and Part E was related to the trustworthiness of the information on social media. In this research, the conceptual framework about the awareness of the use of social media among students was comprised of parts C, D and E that as illustrated in Figure 1 where the questionnaire items

were developed by providing 5-mark scale measurement which were: 1- strongly disagree; 2- disagree; 3-neutral; 4-agree; and 5-strongly agree. It demonstrates the relationship of independent variables towards dependent variable. All the items are tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework awareness of the use of social media among students.

Part	Items	
A	a	Gender
	b	Age
B	a	Have social media account?
	b	Duration of surfing social media per day?
	c	Type of the application of your choice?
	d	Reason for surfing internet/ social media?
C	a	I display information about myself on social media accurately
	b	I display website / email information in social media accurately
	c	I display gender information accurately on social media
	d	I accurately display profile pictures in social media
	e	I accurately display my whereabouts on social media
	f	I accurately display my phone number information on social media
	g	I accurately display my date of birth information on social media
D	a	I make sure the information updated on social media accounts is accurate
	b	I don't have any intention to have a fake social media account to deceive my friends
	c	I don't use rude words throughout the use of social media
E	a	I am a person who is sensitive to the accuracy of social media contact information
	b	I can distinguish the information shared is accurate or false
	c	I have made security settings for my account on social media
	d	I am always aware of who I connect with on social media
	e	I am aware that not all information in social media are true
	f	I always identify the information shared on social media whether it is true or false
	g	I have always been skeptical of information sharing on social media

Questionnaire Design

Table 1: Items for the awareness of the use of social media among students

Data Collection

Cross-nationally comparative data was collected among higher education institutions in Malaysia and Indonesia through an online survey. The respective lecturers (from workshops and virtual classes) gathered the data in January 2021. The questionnaire was a self-administered questionnaire (SAQ) that were designed specifically to be completed by a respondent. The data was collected without any intervention of the researchers and nobody was forced to participate in the survey. The survey was based on voluntary so the students could drop out anytime. This study received feedback from respondents using a questionnaire instrument distributed online through online Google form.

Participants

The number of samples involved in this study included 414 students from Malaysia and Indonesia regardless of their gender and age. They were enrolled in online classes from various disciplines that were not measured in this research.

Data Analysis

The data were analysed with the help of descriptive statistical techniques. Demographic details and analysis of social media usage were reported by frequencies and percentages. The data collection was classified using mean arithmetic, according to the purpose so that meaningful and relevant conclusions could be reached. The higher level of mean showed the high level of transparency in personal data sharing, responsibility in using social media platform and trust in information obtained from social media. The collected data were classified and tabulated, in accordance to the objectives so that the meaningful and relevant inferences by using arithmetic mean could be achieved.

Findings

Part A: Demography

This study involved a total of 414 students consisting of 206 Malaysian students and 209 Indonesian students. Table 2 shows the demographics of the respondents involved in this study.

Demography	Category	Percentage	
		Malaysia	Indonesia
Gender	Male	58.7% (121)	31.2% (65)
	Female	41.3% (85)	68.8% (144)
Age	15 – 19 Years old	0%	93.8% (196)
	20 – 24 Years old	100% (206)	3.3% (7)
	25 – 34 Years old	0%	2.9% (6)

Table 2: Demographics of Respondents

Based on the table above, the demographics of respondents where the number of respondents by gender is 121 male students (58.7%) and 85 female students (41.3%) in Malaysia. For

Indonesian students, there is a total of 65 male students (31.2%) and 144 female students (68.8%). Most of the students who answered the questionnaires were those who had mobile phones and used tech gadgets. For Malaysian students, the selected students were mostly in the age range of 20-24 years, where a total of 205 students answered the questionnaire online. For Indonesian students, the majority who answered the questionnaire was 196 students who were in age range of 15-19 years (93.8%), followed by the age range of 20-24 with 7 students (3.3%) and the last age range of 25-34 years with a total of 6 students (2.9%).

Part B: Analysis of social media usage

This study measured social media usage among Malaysian and Indonesian students. Table 3 shows the percentage of social media usage among them.

No.	Items	Percentage	
		Malaysia	Indonesia
1. Have social media account			
1	Yes	100% (205)	100% (209)
2	No	0%	0%
2. Duration of surfing social media per day			
1	1 – 2 hour (s)	14.6% (30)	29.2% (61)
2	2 – 4 hours	23.4% (48)	59.8% (125)
3	5 – 8 hours	44.9% (92)	11.0% (23)
4	8 – 12 hours	12.7% (26)	0%
5	12 – 16 hours	0.9% (2)	0%
6	> 16 hours	3.41% (7)	0%
3. Type of the application of your choice			
1	Facebook	15.2% (148)	10.0% (21)
2	Instagram	18.3% (179)	76.0% (159)
3	Youtube	17.5% (171)	1.4% (3)
4	Twitter	11.7% (114)	9.1% (19)
5	Whatsapp	18.3% (179)	22.9% (48)
6	Google+	7.7% (75)	0.5% (1)
7	Tik Tok	3.4% (33)	0.5% (1)
8	LinkedIn	1.9% (19)	0%
9	Pinterest	1.9% (19)	0%
10	Skype	1.2% (12)	0%
11	Others	2.9% (28)	0%
4. Reason for surfing internet/ social media			
1	Online games	17.2% (85)	8.13% (17)
2	Searching for information	35.1% (173)	46.8% (98)
3	Avoid boredom	36.1% (178)	46.8% (98)
4	Looking for new acquaintances	11.6% (57)	14.3% (30)

Table 3: Percentage analysis of social media usage

Based on the table above, a summary is highlighted related to the use of social media among students in Malaysia and Indonesia. Based on the data of respondents from Malaysia for question 1, all respondents have all the type of social media (100%). Responses for question 2 showed that the maximum time period for respondents to browse social sites in a day was 5-8 hours (44.9%), followed by 2-4 hours (23.4%) and 8-12 hours (14.6%). This proves that today's youths use social media applications optimally in their daily lives. Next, question 3 was regarding the type of social media application based on the respondent's choice. The most popular social media application was Instagram and WhatsApp application (18%) followed by Youtube (17.5%) and Facebook (15.2%). A total of 36% of the respondents thought that their purpose in surfing the internet / social media was to avoid boredom, followed by 35.1% looking for information and 17.2% playing online games.

As for the data from Indonesian respondents, all the respondents had all the social media types (100%). The maximum time period for respondents to browse social sites in a day was 2-4 hours (44.9%), followed by 1-2 hours (29.2%) and 5-8 hours (11.0%). As for the question of the type of social media application that was the choice of respondents, the most popular social media application was Instagram (76.0%), followed by Whatsapp (22.9%) and Facebook (10.0%). The social media applications that received the lowest response were Google+ and Tik Tok which was 0.5% each. Furthermore, 46.8% of the respondents thought that their purpose of surfing the internet / social media was to find information and avoid boredom.

Most users, especially students, like to share personal information on social media when they are bored without thinking about the negative impact that will occur. The threat or security to their personal information through the Internet is an important issue as it allows users to be at high risk without them realizing it. This is supported by (Lombardi, 2012) where personal information can be easily obtained through social media because there are no restrictions and controls on what to share with others. Therefore, creating the concept of supervision is necessary in overcoming any possibility of happening when interacting with each other through online applications. This not only affects the existence of the concept of surveillance through the Internet network to the individual or the user himself, but also to the economic, political and social of a country (Fuchs, 2012).

Part C: Personal data sharing

The Malaysian students' overall mean score according to both sexes in terms of personal data sharing was higher than Indonesian students with mean score value $M = 2.35$, compared to Indonesian students with the mean score of $M = 2.00$. It showed that the level of transparency of personal data sharing for Indonesian students was lower than the Malaysian student. Figure 2 indicates the personal data sharing that contribute to the awareness of the usage of social media. For Malaysian students, the items that had the highest mean score was "e" (such as, "I accurately display my whereabouts on social media"). According to (Baccarella et al., 2018), sharing the current location on social media could be very dangerous. That is why sharing current location to the current location showed a low awareness of social media usage. For

Indonesian students, the highest mean score was contributed by item “b” (such as, “I display website/email information in social media accurately”). It showed that Indonesian students were more open to show their email address compared to Malaysian students. These parts indicated that they did not want their personal information stolen. This was supported by (Kumar, Gupta, Rai, & Sinha, 2013) who listed several issues related to information security in social media and Internet. Among the risks of information security on the Internet were such as identity theft, phishing or attempts to track someone's banking information to misuse, clone user profiles on the Internet as well as have false sales promotions (Rao, Verma, & Bhatia, 2021). Most Indonesian students were very sensitive towards sharing their personal information on the social media. This was supported by a study (Madden, Lenhart, Cortesi, & Gasser, 2013), which found that 51% of their respondents avoided using some applications on smartphones and tablets due to concerns about their privacy in cyberspace.

Figure 2: Analysis of personal data sharing

Part D: Attitude and behaviour on social media

The Malaysian and Indonesian mean scores for their attitude and behaviour were $M=2.46$ and $M=3.06$, respectively. The Indonesian overall mean score in terms of their attitudes and behaviours in social media was higher than the Malaysian students with the mean score of $M=3.06$. The Malaysian students were likely to use impolite words throughout the use of social media compared to Indonesian students with the mean score of $M=2.46$ for Malaysia students and $M=3.47$ for Indonesian students. This question showed that they had irresponsible attitudes while browsing social media. However, Indonesian students seemed less concerned with the genuineness of information on social media before sharing it with the public. This question showed that they tended to share false information on public. Individuals who encountered false information on social media might actively spread it further, by sharing or otherwise engaging with it (Buchanan, 2020), therefore, individuals must take responsibility to only share the trusted information on social media. Figure 3

depicts the mean score of the Malaysian and Indonesian students' attitudes and behaviours on social media.

Figure 3: Analysis of attitude and behaviour on social media

Part E: Trustworthiness of information on social media

The Malaysian and Indonesian students' mean score for their trustworthiness of the information on social media were $M=2.30$ and $M=2.82$, respectively. The Indonesian students' mean score for this part was higher than the Malaysian students. It showed that the level of trust in information obtained from the social media was for Indonesian students was high compared to Malaysian students. Figure 4 depicts the analysis of trustworthiness of information on social media. Malaysian students' mean score was the highest for item "b" (such as, "I can distinguish the information shared is accurate or false). It showed they had confidence to identify whether the information shared on social media was reliable or not. For Indonesian students, the highest mean score was for item "f" (such as, "I always identify the information shared on social media whether it is true or false). It showed that Indonesian students tended to check first before believing in the information obtained from the social media. This result was consistent with (Syam & Nurrahmi, 2020), which showed that the concerns over fake news had been raised in Indonesia since there had been a significant increase in the spreading of fake news via social media.

Figure 4: Analysis of trustworthiness of information on social media

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study found that users, especially students were aware and understood about issues of privacy and information security while in the virtual world. However, this awareness can only be gained from formal education on the use of media as well as social media. This study has an impact on the importance of media literacy among users ranging from children to adults. Education in Malaysia and Indonesia should integrate the importance of media literacy, ethics of being online, the advantages and disadvantages of new media and so on. Issues of privacy and information security like this should be known by all social media users. If used properly, this media can actually be an effective communication tool, including building understanding between these two allied countries that are sometimes hit by storms due to various issues such as Indonesian Manpower, demarcation problems and so on. When communication can be well built, collaboration and wider networks can be also built more effectively between these two neighbouring countries. There were several limitations to this study. First, the snowball sampling was used as a sample selection procedure where it was not a compelling strategy for selecting a sample that represented the chosen population that satisfied the sampling criteria. However, it was a good tactic for reaching out to a huge number of people with limited movement and time. Second, the accuracy of the findings was heavily dependent on the respondents' honesty, transparency, and cooperation since the sample size and sample spaces were both constrained in this study. The future research should deflect statistical sampling biasness. It is suggested that this study be replicated with students from several colleges or universities in the future. To test the predictive validity of the awareness of the use of social media among students' instrument, it is suggested that a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to be conducted in future so that the instrument's reliability and validity can be verified.

References

1. Ali, S., Islam, N., Rauf, A., Din, I. U., Guizani, M., & Rodrigues, J. J. P. C. (2018). Privacy and security issues in online social networks. *Future Internet*, 10(12), 114.

2. Arno, C. (2012). Worldwide Social Media Usage Trends in 2012, Search Engine Watch.
3. Baccarella, C. V, Wagner, T. F., Kietzmann, J. H., & McCarthy, I. P. (2018). Social media? It's serious! Understanding the dark side of social media. *European Management Journal*, 36(4), 431–438.
4. Barkhuus, L., & Tashiro, J. (2010). Student socialization in the age of Facebook. *Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*.
5. Buchanan, T. (2020). Why do people spread false information online? The effects of message and viewer characteristics on self-reported likelihood of sharing social media disinformation. *Plos One*, 15(10), e0239666.
6. Castells, M. (2011). *The rise of the network society* (Vol. 12). John Wiley & Sons.
7. Chan, E. (2012). Social media an essential ingredient for modern democracy? *ArbitrageMagazine*, Spring, 17–18.
8. Digitalinfluencelab. (2021). Malaysia Digital Marketing Statistics 2021. Retrieved from Digitalinfluencelab website: <https://digitalinfluencelab.com/malaysia-digital-marketing-statistics-2020-2021/>
9. Fuchs, C. (2012). The political economy of privacy on Facebook. *Television & New Media*, 13(2), 139–159.
10. Gerbaudo, P. (2018). Social media and populism: an elective affinity? *Media, Culture & Society*, 40(5), 745–753.
11. GO-Gulf. (2012). How People Spend Their Time Online [Infographic]. Retrieved June 16, 2021, from GO-Gulf website: <https://www.go-gulf.com/online-time/>
12. Kumar, A., Gupta, S. K., Rai, A. K., & Sinha, S. (2013). Social Networking Sites and Their Security Issues. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(4), 1–5.
13. Lombardi, G. (2012). How to map out the perfect, integrated, online marketing strategy for your practice. *Dental Economics*.
14. M.Kaplan, A., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of The World, Unite! The Challengers and Oportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59–68.
15. Madden, M., Lenhart, A., Cortesi, S., & Gasser, U. (2013). Teens and Mobile Apps Privacy. Retrieved from <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2013/08/22/teens-and-mobile-apps-privacy/>
16. Malaysian Communications And Multimedia Commission. (2020). Internet Users Survey 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.mcmc.gov.my/skmmgovmy/media/General/pdf/IUS-2020-Report.pdf>
17. Nielsen. (2019). The Digital Media Habits and Attitudes of Southeast Asian Consumers. Retrieved from <https://www.nielsen.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2019/04/South-East-Asia-Digital-Consumer.pdf>
18. Nurhayati-Wolff, H. (2021). Smartphone users in Indonesia 2017-2026. Retrieved from Statista website: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/266729/smartphone-users-in-indonesia/>
19. Rao, S., Verma, A. K., & Bhatia, T. (2021). Evolving Cyber Threats, Combating Techniques, and Open Issues in Online Social Networks. In *Handbook of Research on Cyber Crime and Information Privacy* (pp. 219–235). IGI Global.
20. Salleh, M. A. M. (2012). The impact of interactivity features in enhancing online communication satisfaction. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 28(2).
21. Salleh, M. A. M., Salman, A., Ali, M. N. S., & Hashim, H. (2016). The importance of usability features in enhancing online communication satisfaction. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 32(1).
22. Syam, H. M., & Nurrahmi, F. (2020). “ I Don ’ t Know If It Is Fake or Real News ” How Little Indonesian University Students Understand Social Media Literacy. *Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 36(2), 92–105.
23. Wollan, R., Smith, N., & Zhou, C. (2011). *The social media management handbook: Everything you need to know to get social media working in your business*. John Wiley & Sons.
24. Yusuf, M. F., Ashari, H., & Razalli, M. R. (2018). Environmental Technological Innovation and Its Contribution to Sustainable Development [J]. *Civil Engineering*, 9(8).